

WELCOME TO OUR

DATA SNACKS

Data Insights in 30 Minutes!

 Get your coffee ready,

 we will start in a few minutes.

**Interactive Visualization in R with Shiny:
Building Your Research Data Skills**

Dr. Maryam Movahedifar | Uni Bremen

**Teach Data, Teach Better: Enhancing
University Teaching with Research Data**

Dr. Susanne de Vogel & Franziska Richter | Uni Bremen

**National High-Performance Computing
(NHR) Roadshow on Digital Humanities**

Anja Gerbes | Uni Göttingen

**Rethinking Research Data Management:
Inclusive Practices for Every Mind**

Sarah Büker | Uni Bremen

Basics of Software Publication

Carina Haupt | DLR

**Beyond ChatGPT: AI Systems for
Qualitative Research**

Nele Fuchs | Uni Bremen

DATA SCIENCE CENTER

Beyond ChatGPT:

AI Systems for Qualitative Research

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04.12.2025 ▪ AI Systems for Qualitative Research

- Qualitative research...
 - ...involves more than just working with non-numerical data.
 - ...generates hypotheses.
 - ...is open to new and unexpected findings during the research process.
 - ...often involves personal and sensitive data, for which the GDPR applies.

- The qualitative research community is having a significant debate about whether using 'AI' in research is justified.
- Open letter, October 2025: "We reject the use of generative artificial intelligence for reflexive qualitative research" (Jowsey et al., 2025)
 - GenAI as simulated intelligence is incapable of meaning making.
 - Qualitative research should remain a distinctly human practice.
 - The established manifold harms of GenAI, especially to the environment and workers in the Global South.
- In summary, there are ethical, methodological, epistemic concerns.

To have a more nuanced discussion, we need to develop stronger technical AI literacy.

“ 'AI' is not a technology but a set of imaginaries and promises.”

(Jürgen Geuter, 2024)

- Today's AI systems can be divided into two groups:

- Pattern recognition

Unlocking smartphone with
fingerprint or Face ID

Spam filter in email inbox

Autocorrection

[...]

- Pattern generation ('genAI')

- Large Language Model (LLM), e.g. GPT5 (ChatGPT), Claude Sonnet 4.5 (Claude) etc.
- Text-to-image model, e.g. Stable Diffusion

- Two key terms: machine learning (ML); natural language processing (NLP)

Deconstructing 'AI'

The application is built around one or more AI models.
➤ Like the car body.

E.g. a large language model.
➤ Like the engine in a car.

High Performance Computing for large models.
Own device for smaller model.
➤ GPU recommended

Deconstructing 'AI'

Deconstructing 'AI'

Using an LLM for Qualitative Research

Using an LLM for Qualitative Research

Using an LLM with RAG for Qualitative Research

Using an LLM with RAG for Qualitative Research

Using an LLM with RAG for Qualitative Research

(Only available to those with access to the services from the GWGD, Göttingen.)

- There are no easy answers to complex ethical and technological questions.
- The qualitative research community should develop a solid digital and AI literacy.
- Collaboration between computer science and qualitative research is essential.
- In order to support this collaboration, we need data competency centers.

AI meets Qualitative Methods

An interdisciplinary network for research with AI

- Network of PhD candidates and postdoctoral researchers.
- The goal is to build competencies in the (responsible) use of AI.
- Regular digital get-togethers; every five to six weeks.

New members are always welcome!

More
information

Jowsey, Tanisha and Braun, Virginia and Clarke, Victoria and Clarke, Victoria and Lupton, Deborah and Fine, Michelle (October 20, 2025). We reject the use of generative artificial intelligence for reflexive qualitative research. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=5676462> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5676462>

Geuter, Jürgen; House of Competence. (June 17, 2024). Jürgen Geuter (tante): Ethische Nutzung von KI. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wnPBmDoMGBc> Slides available: https://ilm-literacy.de/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/Ethische_Nutzung_von_KI.pdf